

Magnitude and Phase Patterns of the Cochlear Partition Vibration on the Cross-section of the Basal Turn in Gerbil Cochleae

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Abstract. Recent low-coherence heterodyne interferometry and optical coherence tomography revealed differences between the reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibration in the sensitive living cochleae. Measurements in the basal cochlear turns in mice and gerbils showed that the reticular lamina vibration is more robust and delayed than the basilar membrane vibration. The reticular lamina and basilar membrane move in the same direction at the best frequency and in opposite directions at low frequencies. However, these results provide limited information on complex motions of different structures within the organ of Corti. To extend the recent findings, we measured the vibration patterns and the structural images on the cross-section of the cochlear partition in the basal turn of living gerbil cochleae. The magnitude and phase patterns of tone-induced vibrations were measured using a scanning heterodyne low-coherence interferometer. The structural images were constructed based on the carrier signal and confirmed by optical coherence tomography. The magnitude patterns show that the low-level tone-induced vibration in the reticular lamina-outer hair cells region is significantly larger than the basilar membrane vibration. The vibration spreads from the peak region to other structures as the sound level increases. The phase patterns reveal in-phase vibrations between the reticular lamina and basilar membrane at the best frequency and anti-phase vibrations at low frequencies. These results suggest sound-induced fluid movements within the tunnel of Corti, outer tunnel, and other extracellular fluid spaces within the organ of Corti in the longitudinal direction, which likely play an essential role in cochlear amplification.

INTRODUCTION

The cochlea can detect various sounds with high sensitivity, sharp frequency selectivity, and huge dynamic range. These cochlear capabilities are commonly thought to result from an outer hair cell-based local feedback mechanism, which amplifies soft sound-induced basilar membrane vibrations [1,2]. As a sound-induced basilar membrane traveling wave propagates from the cochlear base toward the apex [3,4], the shearing motion between the tectorial membrane and the reticular lamina deflects the stereocilia bundle of the outer hair cells. The oscillation of the bundles modulates the conductance of the mechano-electrical transduction channels [5,6], resulting in receptor potential change [7,8]. The trans-membrane potential change alters the conformation of the motile protein, prestin, and generates forces at the stimulus frequency [9,10]. When outer hair cell-generated forces are applied to the basilar membrane at the appropriate time and location, they can increase the basilar membrane responses and boost the cochlear sensitivity [11-14].

To understand how the cochlear feedback works, we measured the sound-induced reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrations as a function of frequency in the basal turns in the mouse and gerbil using a heterodyne low-coherence interferometer [15-17]. Our measurements showed that the tone-induced reticular lamina vibration is significantly larger than the basilar membrane vibration at the best frequency and frequencies far below the best frequency. Contrary to the prediction based on the cochlear local feedback mechanism, the latency of the reticular lamina vibration is greater than that of the basilar membrane vibration. The reticular lamina and basilar membrane move approximately in the same direction at the best frequency and in opposite directions at low frequencies. These

data have been thought to indicate a global hydromechanical mechanism for cochlear amplification [17]. However, the data collected from the reticular lamina and basilar membrane provide limited information on the complex motions of the organ of Corti. This preliminary study measured the vibration patterns on the cross-section of the cochlear partition in the basal turn of living gerbil cochleae. The overlap of vibration patterns and structural images indicated relative motions of different structures within the cochlear partition.

METHODS

Animals and surgical procedures

Healthy Mongolian gerbils (*Meriones unguiculatus*) at the age of 4 to 8 weeks of either sex were used in this study. The experimental protocol was approved by the Oregon Health & Science University Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee. Anesthesia and general surgical procedures were described as previously [18-20]. The auditory bulla on the left side was exposed through a ventrolateral surgical approach, and the lateral 2/3 of the external ear canal was removed. A speculum connected to two speakers and a miniature microphone was coupled to the bony ear canal to form a closed sound field. After the bulla was opened, the cochlea was illuminated using a LED light source through a single-mode optical fiber. A small window was made in the bony lateral wall of the scala tympani in the basal turn using a sharp blade. The landmarks of the cochlear partition and the focal spot of low-coherence light from the interferometer were continuously monitored through a video camera.

Measurement of the cochlear partition vibrations

The measurements were conducted on a vibration-isolation table inside an acoustically attenuated booth. A custom-built scanning heterodyne low-coherence interferometer [13] was used to measure sound-induced cochlear partition vibration in sensitive gerbil cochleae. The interferometer coupled with an upright microscope was mounted on a single-arm boom stand. The animal's head was cemented on a head holder attached to a computer-controlled 3D positioning system. When the basilar membrane was positioned approximately at the horizontal plane, the object beam of the interferometer was focused on the cochlear partition using a long-working-distance objective lens (NA 0.28 or 0.42, 20X, Mitutoyo, Japan) in the basal turn. The light backscattered by the tissues from the focal spot was collected and sent back to the interferometer. The vibration magnitude and direction were determined by detecting the Doppler frequency shift of the backscattered light. The backscattered light level was measured by the carrier signal of the interferometer.

The reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrations were measured at the same cochlear longitudinal location. The transverse locations of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane were indicated by the carrier signal when the focal spot was moved in the transverse direction [13]. When the object beam was focused on the reticular lamina or basilar membrane, the vibration magnitude and phase were measured as a function of frequency at different sound pressure levels. The best frequency of the measured cochlear location was determined by the peak frequency of the reticular lamina or basilar membrane response to low-level tones below 30 dB SPL.

For observing the vibration patterns, the vibration magnitude and phase were measured from different locations on the cross-section of the cochlear partition. The scanning area was $\sim 165 \mu\text{m}$ in the radial direction with $\sim 3\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ scanning steps and $\sim 206 \mu\text{m}$ in the transverse direction with $\sim 3.7\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ scanning steps. The magnitude and phase patterns were obtained at different frequencies and sound pressure levels. The reflectance image of the cochlear partition was constructed based on the carrier signal. The structural image was also obtained using optical coherence tomography from the same cochlear longitudinal location with the same incident angle as for the vibration measurement.

RESULTS

Reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrations at different frequencies

The reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrations measured as a function of frequency from the basal turn of a sensitive gerbil cochlea are presented in Figure 1. At 20 dB SPL (0 dB=20 μ Pa), the displacement of the reticular lamina vibration increased and then decreased with frequency, forming a response peak at \sim 19 kHz, *i.e.*, the best frequency (Fig. 1A). In comparison to the sharply tuned response at low sound levels, the displacement of the reticular lamina response to 80-dB SPL tones decreased with frequency and showed a low-pass pattern. For 60-dB sound pressure increase from 20 to 80 dB SPL, the displacement of the reticular lamina vibration increased by only \sim 15 dB at the best frequency, which indicates a 45-dB compressive nonlinearity. The basilar membrane response to low-level tones also showed a response peak at the same frequency as the reticular lamina vibration (Fig. 1D). The basilar membrane vibration is significantly smaller than the reticular lamina response at low sound pressure levels. At 20 dB SPL, the displacement of the basilar membrane vibration at the best frequency is \sim 20-dB smaller than that of the reticular lamina. This magnitude difference extended toward frequencies far below the best frequency, where the displacement increased proportionally with the sound pressure level. For the same sound level increase (60 dB), the basilar membrane displacement at the best frequency increased by \sim 27 dB, which indicates \sim 12-dB less compression of the basilar membrane vibration than the reticular lamina vibration. The best frequency and nonlinearity of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrations are confirmed by the ratios of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane displacements to the stapes displacement (Figs. 1B and E). The reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibration phase decreased with frequency at an accelerated rate (Figs. 1C and F).

The magnitude difference between the reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibration is presented by the ratio of the reticular lamina to basilar membrane displacement (Fig. 1G). A ratio larger than one indicates that the reticular lamina vibrates more than the basilar membrane. At the best frequency (\sim 19 kHz), the displacement ratio is \sim 10 at 20 dB SPL, decreasing to \sim 1.5 at 80 dB SPL. The largest displacement ratio is at frequencies far below the best frequency and at relatively high sound pressure levels (Fig. 1G). The temporal relationship between the reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibration is shown by the phase difference as a function of frequency (Fig. 1H). The phase difference was obtained by subtracting the basilar membrane phase from the reticular lamina phase at given frequencies. At low frequencies, the phase difference is more than 90 degrees. The phase difference decreased with frequency and approached zero at \sim 15 kHz, reaching \sim 45 degrees at the best frequency. The overlapping solid lines (Fig. 1H) indicate that phase difference does not depend on the sound pressure level.

FIGURE 1. Reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrations at different frequencies in a sensitive gerbil cochlea. (A, B, C) Displacement, the displacement ratio, and phase of the reticular lamina vibration as a function of frequency at 20, 40, 60, and 80 dB SPL. (D, E, F) Displacement, the displacement ratio, and phase of the basilar membrane vibration as a function of frequency at different sound pressure levels. (G) The ratio of reticular lamina displacement to basilar membrane displacement as a function of frequency. (H) Phase difference at different frequencies.

In-phase vibrations of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane at the best frequency

The magnitude and phase patterns of the cochlear partition vibration measured at 20 dB SPL and 25 kHz in a different sensitive cochlea are presented in Fig. 2A and B, and the carrier and structural images are shown in Figs. 2C and D. Since the carrier signal level is determined by the reflection coefficient of the tissue, the carrier signal image

can reveal the structures responsible for the vibrations. The structural image of optical coherence tomography is used to confirm the structures revealed by the carrier image. Together with the structural image of optical coherence tomography, the carrier signal pattern reveals locations of the osseous spiral lamina, tunnel of Corti, outer tunnel, basilar membrane, and the reticular lamina. Despite the limited resolution, the tunnel of Corti, outer tunnel, and reticular lamina can define the outer hair cell region. The magnitude patterns in Fig. 2A show the largest displacement centered at the location of $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ in the radial direction and $\sim 140 \mu\text{m}$ in the transverse direction. The structural images in Fig. 2C and D show that this location is correlated with the reticular lamina-outer hair cell region. The corresponding basilar membrane vibration at $\sim 70\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ transverse location is much smaller than the response peak at the reticular lamina-outer hair cell region. The comparable yellow colors at the measured reticular lamina and basilar membrane locations in Fig. 2B indicate the in-phase motions of those structures. The yellow color across the basilar membrane width shows that the basilar membrane vibration phase does not change significantly in the radial direction.

The magnitude pattern in Fig. 2E shows that, at 80 dB SPL, the vibration spreads to a broad region on the cross-section of the cochlear partition. In addition to the original vibration peak, a concentrated vibration area is at the pectinate zone of the basilar membrane. Except for a small blue strip at the location of $\sim 70 \mu\text{m}$ in the radial direction and $\sim 130\text{-}170 \mu\text{m}$ in the transverse direction, the uniform green color in the phase pattern (Fig. 2F) indicates in-phase motions of the reticular lamina, basilar membrane, and other structures within the cochlear partition. Thus, the data in Figs. 2A-F show that, despite the significant magnitude difference, the phase difference between the reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibration is insignificant and that this phase relationship does not change with the sound pressure level.

Anti-phase vibrations of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane at low frequencies

The vibration patterns within the cochlear partition at low frequencies are significantly different from those at the best frequency. This is shown by the cochlear partition response to a low-frequency high-level tone in Fig. 2G and H. The magnitude pattern measured at 2 kHz and 80 dB SPL in Fig. 2G reveals the largest displacement at the Deiters' cell-outer hair cell junction rather than the reticular lamina-outer hair cell region. The green-red color difference indicates that the displacement of the reticular lamina vibration is significantly larger than the basilar membrane vibration. The sky-blue color at the reticular lamina-outer hair cell region and yellow color in the basilar membrane region in Fig. 2H indicated $\sim 180\text{-degree}$ phase difference between the two locations. Thus, the magnitude and phase patterns in Fig. 2G and H reveal the anti-phase motions between the reticular lamina and basilar membrane at low frequencies and complex motions of different structures within the organ of Corti.

FIGURE 2. Vibration patterns on the cross-section of the cochlear partition. (A and B) Magnitude and phase responses to a 20-dB SPL tone at the best frequency (25 kHz). (C) Carrier signal pattern. (D) Structural image of the organ of Corti acquired using optical coherence tomography. (E and F) The magnitude and phase patterns at 25 kHz and 80 dB SPL. (G and H) The magnitude and phase patterns at 2 kHz and 80 dB SPL. RL: reticular lamina; BM: basilar membrane; TC: tunnel of Corti; OT: outer tunnel; OSL: osseous spiral lamina.

CONCLUSIONS

The magnitude and phase patterns of the cochlear partition vibration show that the reticular lamina vibration is significantly larger than the basilar membrane vibration. The reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibrate approximately in the same direction at the best frequency and in opposite directions at low frequencies. These results are consistent with the recent findings in gerbils using heterodyne low-coherence interferometry [15-17] and optical coherence tomography [21-27]. The present data also reveal the complex motions of different structures within the cochlear partition. The relative motions among the reticular lamina, basilar membrane, and other structures suggest sound-induced fluid movements in the longitudinal direction within the tunnel of Corti, outer tunnel, and other extracellular spaces within the organ of Corti, which likely play an essential role in the cochlear amplification. This *in vivo* hydromechanical mechanism is consistent with the outer hair cell-induced longitudinal flow movement within the organ of Corti *in vitro* [28] and the proposed sound-induced area change of the organ of Corti [29].

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REFERENCES

1. P. Dallos, *J. Neurosci.* **12**, 4575-4585 (1992).
2. L. Robles, M. A. Ruggero, *Physiol. Rev.* **81**, 1305-1352 (2001).
3. T. Ren, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **99**, 17101-17106 (2002).
4. J. A. Fisher, F. Nin, T. Reichenbach, R. C. Uthaiyah, A. J. Hudspeth, *Neuron* **76**, 989-997 (2012).
5. D. P. Corey, A. J. Hudspeth, *Nature* **281**, 675-677 (1979).
6. R. Fetipace, C. M. Hackney, *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* **7**, 19-29 (2006).
7. P. Dallos, J. Santos-Sacchi, A. Flock, *Science* **218**, 582-584 (1982).
8. I. J. Russell, *Nature* **301**, 334-336 (1983).
9. W. E. Brownell, C. R. Bader, D. Bertrand, Y. de Ribaupierre, *Science* **227**, 194-196 (1985).
10. J. Zheng *et al.*, *Nature* **405**, 149-155 (2000).
11. F. Chen *et al.*, *Nat. Neurosci.* **14**, 770-774 (2011).
12. J. B. Dewey, A. Altoe, C. A. Shera, B. E. Applegate, J. S. Oghalai, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **118** (2021).
13. T. Ren, W. He, P. G. Barr-Gillespie, *Nat. Commun.* **7**, 10282 (2016).
14. M. Nowotny, A. W. Gummer, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **103**, 2120-2125 (2006).
15. T. Ren, W. He, D. Kemp, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **113**, 9910-9915 (2016).
16. W. He, D. Kemp, T. Ren, *Elife* **7**, e37625 (2018).
17. W. He, G. Burwood, A. Fridberger, A. L. Nuttall, T. Ren, *Hear. Res.* 10.1016/j.heares.2021.108407, 108407 (2021).
18. W. He, A. Fridberger, E. Porsov, K. Grosh, T. Ren, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **105**, 2729-2733 (2008).
19. T. Ren, A. L. Nuttall, *Hear. Res.* **151**, 48-60 (2001).
20. T. Ren, *Nat. Neurosci.* **7**, 333-334 (2004).
21. N. P. Cooper, A. Vavakou, M. van der Heijden, *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 3054 (2018).
22. A. Vavakou, N. P. Cooper, M. van der Heijden, *Elife* **8** (2019).
23. E. Fallah, C. E. Strimbu, E. S. Olson, *Hear. Res.* **377**, 271-281 (2019).
24. W. Dong *et al.*, *J. Neurophysiol.* 10.1152/jn.00702.2017 (2018).
25. C. E. Strimbu, Y. Wang, E. S. Olson, *Biophys. J.* **119**, 2087-2101 (2020).
26. N. H. Cho, H. Wang, S. Puria, *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol* **23**, 195-211 (2022).
27. S. W. F. Meenderink, W. Dong, *Commun. Biol.* **5**, 1285 (2022).
28. K. D. Karavtiki, D. C. Mountain, *Biolphs. J.* **92**, 3284-3293 (2007).
29. J. J. Guinan *Hear. Res.* **426**, 108641 (2022).

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Aleks Zosuls]: Please find my comments annotated inline with your draft in the attached PDF.

1. What is the size of the hole you made in the lateral wall?
2. What is the component of OoC displacement you are measuring? Is it transverse, radial, or a mix?

3. Are Figs. 1G and H on the same frequency scale? The phase appears to end at 22.5 kHz and the Magnitude at 25 kHz.
4. What is the phase reference for Figs. 1C and E?
5. Longitudinal fluid flow within the organ of Corti has been proposed and modeled by others. Your conclusion would be stronger with a reference or two on the topic.
6. Very nice work! The use of two imaging modalities to confirm the anatomy is cool. It is understood that MoH papers are often work in progress or preliminary. What is the N of your results in this paper? Are the results and trends consistent across animals? Have you measured and can you comment on what happens after the animal dies? Especially the RL vs BM magnitude and phase ratio differences?

[Tianying Ren]: Thanks for your thoughtful comments and suggestions. Here are our responses to your comments.

1. Approximately 250 μm wide and 350 μm long.
2. The displacement was measured in the transverse direction. The opening in the lateral wall allows the object beam to access the cochlear partition in the transverse direction. This was confirmed by the video image through the microscope and structural images in Figs. 2C and D.
3. Figs. 1G and H are on the same frequency scale. The phase values above 22.5 kHz were removed because they became random due to the low magnitude.
4. The phase reference is the stapes footplate vibration.
5. Thanks, and we have cited Karavitaki and Mountain's work in the revised manuscript.
6. Data in Figs. 1 and 2 are representative results from sensitive cochleae. These data are consistent across animals. Low-level RL and BM responses disappeared immediately after the animal died. While BM responses to intermediate and high-level stimuli decreased only at frequencies near the BF, the RL vibrations decreased by ~ 20 dB at all frequencies. There is no significant magnitude or phase difference between the RL and BM vibrations in the dead cochleae. For more details, please see our previous publications (Fig. 2 by Ren et al. PNAS, 2016; Fig. 2 by He et al. eLife 2018).

[C. Elliott Strimbu]: These are very nice data. The heat map/areal vibration patterns shown in Figure 2 are similar to what we have seen in the base of the gerbil cochlea. It is reassuring that another technique yields similar results. I have a couple of questions:

1. How long are the individual measurements? Does your system use the carrier signal to create the structural images (such as Figure C) at the same time that it takes the vibration measurements? You said that the measurements presented in Figure 2 were taken in 3 micron steps; does your system step in both the radial and transverse directions and take one measurement at each radial/transverse location? About how long does a complete set of measurements then take?
2. In Figure 2, it seems that there is detectable motion in the "Tectorial Membrane Region"--that is vibrations where the TM is located based on the morphology, although the TM is quite transparent at these wavelengths. It is especially pronounced in panels A & B and E & F which are close to the BF. I'm asking because we sometimes see something like this in the "TM-region" even if the TM is itself barely visible in the Bscans.
3. The structural images in Figure 2 suggest that the view of the organ of Corti is primarily transverse. Would it be possible to do something similar to Frost et al. (JASA 2022) to measure the orientation of the organ of Corti with respect to the optical axis using your system?

[Tianying Ren]: Thank you for the thoughtful comments. It is nice to know that our 2D data measured using the heterodyne low-coherence interferometer (Fig. 2) are similar to your OCT data.

1. It takes ~ 24 to 30 minutes to collect a complete data set. Yes, our system uses the carrier signal to create the structural images (such as Fig. 2C). The carrier signal, vibration magnitude, and phase are recorded at the same time from each radial/transverse location with a 3- or 3.7- μm separation.
2. You are correct that the vibration magnitude is visible at the tectorial membrane location in Figs. 2A, B, E, and F, although the tectorial membrane itself is invisible in the structural images (Figs. 2C and D). This is likely caused by the fact that the vibration measurement is more sensitive than the reflectivity detection in our system. It is encouraging to know that you sometimes see TM vibration, even the TM itself is barely visible in the OCT Bscans.
3. It would be nice if we could measure the orientation of the organ of Corti with respect to the optical axis, as Frost et al. (2022) demonstrated using OCT. However, the data collected using our system do not have volumetric information, which is required for Frost et al.'s analysis. Moreover, we measured the cochlear partition vibration in the transverse direction through the opening in the lateral wall.

[Wei Dong]: It is interesting to see how you have continuously improved the low-coherence heterodyne interferometry into a scanning system to map the vibrations of the cross-section of the organ of Corti complex.

The magnitudes in the outer tunnel (OT) and tunnel of Corti (TO) regions in Figures 2F and 2G appeared above the noise floor. Are these values real, or could they be due to the interpretation of the data points? If the motions in these regions are within the noise, it might be better to change those areas to blank. The same applies to the phase responses. Furthermore, it would be beneficial to include a discussion paragraph to elaborate on the interplay between different regions and compare these findings to other studies in the literature.

[Tianying Ren]: Thanks for your insightful comments.

The scanning measurement of the cochlear partition vibration is an inherent capability of the low-coherence heterodyne interferometer. We did not report the scanning data previously due to the uncertain relationship between the incident angle of the object beam and the structures within the cochlear partition.

We agree with you that the magnitudes in the outer tunnel and tunnel of Corti regions in Figures 2E and G are above the noise floor. These are real vibration magnitudes, which is supported by phase data in Figures 2F and H. The phase values would have become random if the vibration magnitude were below the noise. Magnitude and phase values in Figures 2E, F, G, and H are raw data without interpolation.

As a result of your suggestion, we have expanded the discussion.